

CASE REPORT

Endodontic and prosthodontic rehabilitation of a fractured maxillary canine: A case report

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Abstract

The rehabilitation of severely fractured teeth is a reasonable issue in restorative dentistry. This article presented a case of a 26-year-old male patient with a fractured maxillary canine. Considerably, the conventional method used for repair of the canine tooth with inadequate coronal structure was achieved consecutively by setting up smile esthetics and support for prosthetics through the involvement of a root canal treatment, a post and cost system, and a porcelain-fused-to-metal crown.

Keywords root canal therapy, gingivectomy, tooth fracture, tooth crown, crown lengthening

1 | Introduction

Predominantly, tooth fractures involve upper front teeth due to their position in the mouth.¹ The nature of failures of the tooth structure is associated with high sugar consumption leading to caries severity² and food characteristics as the food particle's mechanical properties are likely to induce deformation at the tooth surface.³ The investigation established that a tiny bit of hardness >2.5 times that of enamel has its effect to a large

extent on the surface, sliding against it at depleted forces, causing a break to the coronal structure.⁴ Hence, depending on the incident, the tooth may be chipped off, dislocated, or even knocked out in the oral cavity.¹ Even though central and lateral incisors have the maximum effect on the appearance while smiling, the visibility of the mesial part of maxillary canines still impacts smile esthetics. Canine fractures necessitate a responsive treatment for functional and cosmetic restoration.⁵

As aforementioned, the severity and consequences of the tooth fracture can range from minor to severe, needing no treatment to RCT or even tooth loss, respectively.⁶ Endodontics and prosthodontics are handed in hand to treat badly broken-down teeth that would have otherwise seemed fit for dental extraction.⁷ Some studies have shown that in the pre-adhesive era, the rehabilitation of fractured teeth was one or the other with pin-retained inlays or cast restoration followed by full-coverage crowns.⁸ Nevertheless, when the pulp chamber is involved, the tooth would need RCT and post and core system. Correct fabrication of post and core and a crown can add to the success rate of reconstructions.⁹ The considerations of the class of facial and lingual tooth contours, the size, and the suitability of existing restorations are some of the factors incomparable to surveyed crowns.¹⁰ This case report described the endodontic and prosthodontic management of a fractured maxillary canine tooth.

2 | Case presentation section

2.1. Chief complaint

A 26-year-old male patient presented to the dental office with the chief complaint of a broken upper right canine. He described the appearance as unattractive and unpleasant. Maxillary right canine (#13) was damaged due to weakened tooth structure from severe dental caries and biting on hard food (Figure 1).

2.2. Medical & dental history

A relatively healthy 26-year-old male patient with a noncontributory medical history. Dental history of multiple missing teeth (#17, #16, #14, #12, #11, #21, #22, #24, #25, #26, #27, #28, #37, #36, #35, #44, #46, #47, & #48) that was treated with removable partial denture with metal framework, composite restoration on tooth #13, #15, #45, #34 and #38, and a jacket crown on #23.

Figure 1. (A) Fractured upper right canine acted with a part as an (B) abutment for a removable partial denture on the affected arch.

2.3. Diagnosis & etiology

On examination, there was a notice of caries on #13 that triggered a complicated fracture upon a bite of hard food. Also, there was no mobility on the affected tooth and no apparent trauma to the tissues. However, there was a presence of pulpal exposure. Hence, the tooth had left around 2 mm to 3 mm ferrule above the gingiva.

2.4. Prognosis

A fractured mono-rooted canine with a character as an abutment for removable prosthetics had a poor prognosis for extraction and reconstruction of the denture without minimally invasive way, but a good prognosis for related treatment, root canal therapy with a porcelain-fused-to-metal crown (PFM). The dentist recommended the latter option, preferably aligned with the patient's

limited budget and retainment of #13. Hence, the prognosis was favorable because of the dentist's expertise and intensive treatment plan. Also, the patient's proper maintenance would play a role in the surviving esthetic and functional restoration outcome on #13.

2.5. Treatment

Based on findings, canine extraction was not advisable. Thus, the indicated treatments were endodontic and prosthodontic therapies. The preliminary treatment plan focused on non-surgical periodontal management and root canal therapy (Figure 2) using a pro tapered crown-down file method with a 23 mm working length. The dentist instructed the patient to return after two weeks for the continuation process. The second treatment plan was a post and core system wherein the establishment of a core for tooth # 13 was usually over with dual cure

Figure 2. Root canal procedure on tooth #13. Cleaning and shaping of root canal (A). Placement of calcium hydroxide as an intracanal medicament in the root canal (B). Completion of the obturation process (C).

composite for cementation and core build-up. There was a suggestion for gum cautery due to excess gum tissues surrounding the tooth with the execution of tooth preparation for the crown and impression taking at the same meeting. After a month, the dentist advised the patient to return for a PFM crown (Figure 3). Before the patient's permanent restoration, the dentist conducted the installment of a temporary jacket crown to avoid fracture and failure of the post and core. There were indications for recall and post-operative care for the patient.

3 | Discussion

Excessive loss of tooth structure required consideration of the esthetic zone and biomechanical stability.¹¹ In the case of the patient with the destructed coronal structure on tooth # 13, glass fiber post-and-core build-up was necessary to restore the bulk of the coronal portion of the fractured canine. Afterward, a PFM crown on the root canal-treated tooth acted as an abutment for the removable partial denture. Here, we evaluated the

Figure 3. Root canal treatment on tooth #13 (A). Post and core in preparation for crown build-up (B). Completion of gingivectomy and tooth build-up (C). Placement of a porcelain-fused-to-metal (PFM) crown (D).

fracture resistance and long-term survival of a glass fiber post-and-core build-up canine.

The purpose of using a post is to provide anchorage, stability, and retention for a core to maintain the coronal restoration of the fractured tooth. Research has shown that for a successful post-and-core, certain factors should be considered related to the percentage of root in the bone, tooth position, cement, and type of restoration.¹² Post length, diameter, and design also influence post survival.¹³ The biomechanical stability of the glass fiber post-and-core was assessed by the presence of the ferrule design to provide more satisfactory stress distribution to the canine roots.¹⁴ In addition, the advantage of a glass fiber post to a cast post-and-core and carbon fiber post was that the former is more resistant to fracture loads.¹⁵ Lastly, root canal-treated tooth restored with fiber posts and PFM has higher survival rates than PFM reconstructed without fiber posts.¹⁶

4 | Conclusions

The substances of visual and functional roles heightened the restoration of fractured teeth. Considerably, the conventional method used for rehabilitation of a root canal-treated #13 with inadequate tooth structure was achieved consecutively by setting up smile esthetics and support for

removable prosthetics on the affected arch through the involvement of a post and core system and a PFM crown. It also called attention to the requirement of thorough planning and meticulous execution of the treatment of the fractured canine.

Institutional Review Board Statement

The study was conducted in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki, and approved by the Ethics Committee of Southwestern University PHINMA School of dentistry.

Informed Consent Statement

Informed consent was obtained from the patient and the attending dentist. All methods have been exhausted to maintain the anonymity of the patient.

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Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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